

Australia → ESO → 4MOST → WAVES → GAMA → CSFH

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University of Western Australia

Perth

Australia to become an ESO Strategic Partner for the next 10 years
Access to VLT and La Silla, with view to full membership in 2027

New route to Chile?

Perth - Sydney - Canberra - Melbourne

Australian Science

Redshift surveys

Fibre positioners

- FLAMES
- EFMOS
- AAOMEGA
- AESOP
- Starbugs

SAMI Hector IFU Science

HI and continuum surveys

Reionisation, Pulsars & FRBs

2dFGRS

2dFGRS
SDSS

2dFGRS
SDSS
6dF

2dFGRS
SDSS
6dF
MGC

VVDS
VUDF

2dFGRS
SDSS
6dF
MGC
zCOSMOS

VVDS
VUDF

2dFGRS
SDSS
6dF
MGC
zCOSMOS
DEEP2

VVDS
VUDF

2dFGRS
SDSS
6dF
MGC
zCOSMOS
DEEP2
VIPERS

VVDS
VUDF

2dFGRS
SDSS
6dF
MGC
zCOSMOS
DEEP2
VIPERS
GAMA

9hrs

15hrs

3hrs

21hrs

2 4 6 8 10
Lookback time (Gyrs)

VVDS
VUDF

2dFGRS
SDSS
6dF
MGC
zCOSMOS
DEEP2
VIPERS
GAMA
TAIPAN

VVDS
VUDF

2dFGRS
SDSS
6dF
MGC
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VVDS
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MOONS
PFS

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GAMA
TAIPAN
DEVILS
WAVES

4-metre Multi-Object Spectroscopic Telescope (4MOST)

- **€60 Million upgrade to the 4m VISTA telescope to become large field of view fibre-fed spectroscopic survey facility**

- 2400 fibres over 4deg²
- 1600 low-res (3700-9500Å, R~5000)
- 800 high-res (3 windows, R~18,500)
- 1.45'' fibre diameter
- Consortium members:

Australia's Contribution: AESOP

- AAO is building the positioner: Australian-European Southern Observatory Positioner (AESOP)
- Funded by AAO (\$1M in kind), Aus Universities (~\$800k), and Australian Research Council (\$560+\$440)

WAVES partner institutions:

4MOST: Nine Consortium Surveys

- Will run 10 consortium surveys (70%) and community surveys (30%) contiguously over 5yrs (+public), >60M sources!

1. Milky Way Halo $R > 5,000$ (~3M stars) - Helmi & Irwin
 - Chemo-dynamical streams
2. Milky Way Halo $R > 20,000$ (~0.2M stars) - Christleib
 - Chemical evolution of accreted components
3. Milky Way disks/bulge $R > 5,000$ (~25M stars) - Chiappini, Minchev, Starkenburg
 - Chemo-dynamics of disk and bulge
4. Milky Way disks/bulge $R > 20,000$ (~2.5M stars) - Bergemann, Bensby
 - Chemical evolution of in-situ components
5. eROSITA galaxy clusters (~50,000 clusters, ~2.5M galaxies) - Finoguenov
 - Dark Energy cluster/galaxy evolution
6. eROSITA AGN (~1M galaxies) - Merloni
 - Evolution of AGN and their host galaxies
7. WAVES (~2M galaxies) - Driver & Liske
 - Galaxy Evolution
8. Cosmology (~23M galaxies) - Kneib & Richard
 - Luminous red and blue galaxies. Absorption systems
9. Magellanic system survey (~1M stars) - Cioni
 - Chemo-dynamics of clouds, variable stars
10. TiDES (Transients) - Nichol
 - Live transients, SNe hosts, AGN monitoring

Dark Matter is King (Time < 9Gyrs)

Time since Big Bang 0.1

Time since Big Bang 9

Time since Big Bang 6

Time since Big Bang 13.3

WAVES: Motivation And Aims

- Probe the **dark matter** domain using groups
- Explore the **dark matter-baryon interface**
- Provide an **empirical blueprint of galaxy evolution** since $z=1$
- Provide a unique **legacy resource** for diverse galaxy studies

WAVES Science: Dark Matter

- Construction of robust pair, group and filament catalogue
- All $M > 2 \times 10^{12} M_{\odot}/h$ halos at $z < 0.2$ robustly detected
- Combine with weak lensing from VST-KiDS/ Euclid

- Robust comparison to new numerical, semi-analytic and hydro simulations....

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WAVES Science: Dark Matter

Will “directly detect” 40% of all DM within our $z < 0.1$ volume via group finding & velocity dispersion

WAVES Science: Groups

Halo Mass Function constraints at bright and faint end

WAVES Science: DM-Baryon Interface

Merger rates νz

Mass fns by component

LSBG searches

- Halo occupation statistics, star-formation efficiency, merger rates, environmental quenching, etc

- Assembly of Stellar Mass and Structure

- Charting the low-mass, LSB Universe.

WAVES Science: Empirical Blueprint of Evolution

- Evolution of mass, energy and structure over an 8Gyr baseline
- Bridge the local ($z < 0.3$, SDSS/GAMA) & distant ($z > 1$, MOONS) Universe... [WAVES-deep]
- ..and high mass (SDSS/GAMA) & low mass (local volume) Universe [WAVES-wide]

WAVES as a Legacy Resource

WAVES: Multi-wavelength

WAVES as a Legacy Resource

- **JWST** - Intermediate redshift ($z \sim 0.7$) groups in **WAVES-deep**, optimal foreground lenses for the $z > 10$ Universe
- **Euclid/W-FIRST** - Robust bulge-disc decompositions for all **WAVES-deep** galaxies, evolution of structure to $z \sim 1$
- **eROSITA** - Optically selected group stacking to extend scaling relations to much lower masses

• **ASKAP/SKA** - WALLABY/EMU data for all of **WAVES**, **WAVES-deep**/DINGO overlap. Optically motivated source finding/stacking + environment.....

WAVES: Survey Design

astromap.icrar.org

WAVES wide

- $z < 21.5$ & photo- $z < 0.2$
- 1350deg² KiDS
- ~1M targets, > 95% complete
- Stellar mass to $\sim 10^6 M_\odot$
- Groups to $10^{10} M_\odot$

WAVES deep

- $z < 21.5$
- 2x50deg² regions
- ~1M targets, > 95%
- GALEX, H-ATLAS, Euclid, DINGO
- Evolution to $z \sim 0.8$

GAMA: FINAL DATA RELEASE, LEGACY, AND FUTURE GALAXY EVOLUTION SURVEYS

HOME / CONFERENCES / GAMA: FINAL DATA RELEASE, LEGACY, AND FUTURE GALAXY EVOLUTION SURVEYS

<http://www.icrar.org/conferences/gamaworkshop/>

FIVE-DAY MEETING

ICRAR-UWA

NOVEMBER 6-10TH, 2017

The Galaxy And Mass Assembly (GAMA) is a decade long project to probe the evolution of mass, energy and structure on scales ranging from 1kpc to 1Mpc – measuring properties of the internal structures of galaxies, interacting pairs and mergers, the group environment and large-scale structure. While the GAMA team has produced multiple seminal results, there is a wealth of data yet to be exploited within the GAMA database. As such, this year the extensive dataset produced by the GAMA team, including deep spectroscopic observations and 21-

- GAMA
- WAVES
- DEVILS
- Taipan
- MOONS
- SAMI
- HECTOR
- WEAVE
- PFS
- HSC
- eRosita
- MSE
- EMU
- GLASS
- GLEAM
- DINGO
- LSST
- WFIRST
- H-ATLAS
- KiDs
- Wallaby
- ESO 12m
- SURFs

Filaments

GAMA Group catalogue Full Release 5000 groups with $N > 5$

Groups

$0.15 < z < 0.2$
 $-1 < \text{Dec} < 0$

G12

Redshift ↑

° $N = 2$
○ $N = 5$
○ $N = 10$

FACT: 50% of stellar mass at z=0 is in discs, 50% in spheroids

Stellar mass by galaxy component

Moffett et al (2016)

Probably bound !

Galaxy stellar mass function

Wright et al (2017)

Plot of the Week!

Madau & Dickinson (2014)

Can we use a single tracer across all time?

GAMA + COSMOS + 3DHST: 600,000 galaxies $0 < z < 5$

MAGPHYS (UV-far-IR) analysis adopting a fixed Chabrier IMF

Madau & Dickinson (2014)

z=0.05 GAMA galaxy

z=1.0 COSMOS galaxy

600,000 galaxies fitted with MAGPHYS from $0 < z < 5$

GAMA + COSMOS + 3DHST: 600,000 galaxies $0 < z < 5$

MAGPHYS analysis using fixed Chabrier IMF

Note time axis: more fundamental for discussing SF

GAMA + COSMOS + 3DHST: 600,000 galaxies $0 < z < 5$

MAGPHYS analysis using fixed Chabrier IMF

Various numerical predictions v new data

GAMA + COSMOS + 3DHST: 600,000 galaxies $0 < z < 5$

MAGPHYS analysis using fixed Chabrier IMF

Spline fit

GAMA + COSMOS + 3DHST: 600,000 galaxies $0 < z < 5$

MAGPHYS analysis using fixed Chabrier IMF

Integration of the spline: Replenishment of 0.49 needed

GAMA + COSMOS + 3DHST: 600,000 galaxies $0 < z < 5$

MAGPHYS analysis using fixed Chabrier IMF

Cosmic Dust Density: 95% of all dust destroyed

THE HUBBLE DEEP FIELD CORE SAMPLE ($I < 26.0$)

Simon Driver & Alberto Fernandez-Soto (UNSW)

Driver et al (1998)

Two phase model: Axioms

Driver et al (2013)
Andrews et al (2017)

- AGN activity traces spheroid formation
- Spheroid formation dominates at high-z

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